

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Triyandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol. XIV, Book. III -IV

JULY - DECEMBER 2022

SRF

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohanam

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohanam@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

dr.rjinu@gmail.com

Contents

The tantric concept in “Vātāpi Gaṇapatiṃ bhaje”-A study	Dr.Pradeep Varma.P.K	7
Śākta Brahmins of Kerala and their rituals with esoteric and exoteric dimensions	Dr. Ajithan. P. I	14
Lanka’s Princess as an Art of Reclaiming Beauty	Dr. M S Gayathri Devi	37
Role of Ayurveda in Geriatric Nutrition	Dr. Gopikrishnan P. T., ,Dr. Haritha Chandran,	
	Dr. Haroon Irshad	51
Manuscriptology: An Overview -	Dr. Keerthi P, Prof. Ramadas P.V. Dr. Haritha Chandran,	
	Dr. Leena P.Nair	58
Spell Checker for Sanskrit Sentences based on Morphological Analysis-	Dr. Namrata Tapaswi	66
Appreciation of Muttusvami Dikshitar’s Navāvaraṇa Kṛti in the Raga Śāṅkarabharanam. -	Mr. Ratheesh P R	77
A Reference Frame for Self-Studies and Self-Regulatory Mechanism of Vedas: Personality Changes - [Swami Parmarth Dev,	Sadvi Dev Priya, Anjali Prabhakar and Paran Gowda]	85
Taxation in Dharmaśāstra -	Dr. Tarak Jana	100
Developmental Stages of <i>Camatkāra</i> in Sanskrit Poetics	Dr. Sudip Chakravortti	114
Elevating the modern educational experience: Correlating ‘Practical Vedanta’ and ‘Bratacārī’ -	Dr Anusrita Mandal	124
Dharma: The Bed Rock of Social Philosophy of Renaissance Thinkers of Kerala. -	Rakesh. K	134
The Concept of Pratibhā and its Implications; Gleanings from Vākyapadīya -	Dr. Sarath P Nath	144
Vaijayantikośa- Nature and Methodology-	Athira.T	153
Analytical study of Śabda -	Dr.N.S.Sharmila	167
Temple architecture: Classification and characteristics	Dr S Radhakrishnan	173
Knowledge of the Heart in Ādi Śāṅkarācārya’s Upaniṣad Commentary	Jyothi. L	181
The Tradition of Nyaya in Kerala -	Niveditha Sathyan	187
Drona: The Practitioner of Injustice -	Dr. G. Reghukumar	195
Karma Yoga Concept in Shrimad Bhagavad Gita: A Conceptual Frame Development - Anjali Prabhakar and Paran Gowda		202
Śrī Jagannāth and Vaiṣṇavism -	Dr.Nilachal Mishra	211
Morals and Teaching of Values for Human Being in Shrimad Bhagavad Gita -	Ramesh Kumar Awasthi	217

Status of Women Depicted in Manusmriti -	Dr. Shylaja S	223
Authoritative Works on Rāja Yoga - A Brief Reflective		
	Sunitha S.	235
Rig Veda and Astronomy -	Girish V.	242
Traces of Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara in the Śaiva Scriptures of Odisha -	Dr. Anil Kumar Acharya	247
तत्त्वशास्त्रे चित्सुखप्रकाशितं स्वप्रकाशत्वमित्यद्वैततत्त्वम् -	डा.सि.आर् सन्तोष	260
श्रीहरिनामामृतपाणिनीयव्याकरणयोरचसन्धिप्रकरणस्य तुलनात्मकमध्ययनम्	डॉ. प्रीतिलक्ष्मी स्वाई	271
कुमारसम्भवस्य तिङन्तपदानि - मल्लिनाथीयविवेचनम् - विश्वबन्धु उपाध्यायः		278
योगवासिष्ठरामायणे शास्त्रव्याख्यानकौशलविमर्शः-	अमृता घोषः	282
उपनिषदि ब्रह्मस्वरूप-विमर्शः	अम्बरीष दासः	289
रसगङ्गाधरे नव्यन्यायभाषाशैली	डा. के. रतीष	294
धातुवृत्तयः धातुकोशाश्च	डॉ. जयदेवदिण्डा	298
वाक्यपदीये वाक्यस्वरूपम्	ड० मलयपोडे	312
मनुसंहितालिखितायां समाजव्यवस्थायां नारीणां पदम् : दूषणं तत्प्रतिकारश्च		
	प्रशान्त कर्मकार	320
वैयाकरणमतमनुसृत्य प्रतिभास्वरूपविचारः	डा० राजीवः पी. पी	329
ज्योतिर्गणितपद्धतीनां परिचयः	डा. हरिनारायणन्	334
अद्वैतनयेसत्तास्वरूपविमर्शः	डा. निषाद टि. एस्	339
भवभूतेकृतिषु सांख्ययोगमीमांसादर्शनतत्त्वानामन्वेषणम् -	डा० तानिया सिकदार	342
पाणिनीयव्याकरणे सूत्राणामेकवाक्यताविमर्शः -	डॉ. मनीषकुमारझाः	347
सर्वङ्गषाटीकायां व्याकरणालोचने मल्लिनाथस्य कतिपयाऽनवधानता - मृत्युञ्जयगराँड		354
परमपुरुषार्थसिद्धये भक्तिमार्गः	शुभाङ्कर बसकः	361
कातन्त्रव्याकरणसूत्रपरिचयः	डा० टि. वि गिरिजा	367
अष्टाध्याय्यां विभाषाधिकारेऽपि नित्यसमासविधानम्	पङ्कजराउलः	370
अलुक्समासविमर्शः	राजकुमार-मण्डलः	374
मधुसूदनसरस्वतीप्रणीते कृष्णकुतूहले भक्तिरसविमर्शः -	रिक्ता मण्डलः	380
जैनरीत्या बौद्धसम्मतप्रमाणलक्षणसमीक्षणम् -	श्रीशशांकशेखरपालः	388
जनकल्याणे नीतिशतकस्य माहात्म्यम्	समीरणः रायः	396
विभावना-विशेषक्तयोः समीक्षात्मकपर्यालोचनम्	शान्तनुः प्रधानः	401
संस्कृतव्याकरणदिशा ओडिआभाषायाः समीक्षणम् -	शिवानन्द बेहेरा	403
आचार्यधर्मकीर्तिकृतविविधसम्बन्धस्वरूपदूषणं तन्निराकरणञ्च -	सुजन-दासः	409
कादम्बरीहर्षचरितयोर्बाणभद्रस्य काव्यसौन्दर्यम्- प्रो. प्रसूनदत्तसिंहः, सुपर्णा सेनः		414
शिवसङ्कल्पः स्वरूपश्च पौराणिकग्रन्थेषु	डा. बिन्दुश्री के. एस्	419
न्यायसिद्धान्तमुक्तावल्यानुसारेण शब्दप्रमाणनिरूपणम् -	अश्वति एस्	422
वराहमिहिरस्य जीवचरितम् -	बि. नागराजः, डा. यादव	429
उपनिषद्ग्रन्थेषु पर्यावरणम्- एकमध्ययनम्	डा० गोविन्दसर्कार	432
रामायणमहाकाव्ये मोक्षस्य अवधारणा	तरणीकुमारपण्डा	437
अक्षपाददर्शनम्	डा. एस्. शिवकुमारः	445
सांख्ययोगौ पृथग्बालाः प्रवदन्ति न पण्डिताः	डा. अरविन्दमहापालः	451
Submission & Subscription		460

Role of Ayurveda in Geriatric Nutrition

Dr. Gopikrishnan P. T.¹,

Dr. Haritha Chandran², Dr. Haroon Irshad³

Introduction

Gerontology is the study of the biological, psychological, and social aspects of ageing. Gerontology research involves the study of normal ageing processes and age-related diseases.

Jara is an inescapable part of life. Jara Chikitsa or Rasayana is a unique therapeutic methodology to delay ageing and minimise the intensity of problems occurring in this degenerative phase of one's life. The hour demands to develop an effective holistic protocol for geriatric care by combining Rasayana, Panchakarma, Dietetics, Ayurvedic medicines, lifestyle and Yoga.

Good nutrition means “maintaining a nutritional status that enables us to grow well and enjoy good health”. Those who take proper diet live a long life.

Concept of Jara in Ayurveda

Svabhavabalapravrutta Vyadhi like Kshudha, Pipasa, Nidra, Jara and Mrityu are described according to Acharya Susrutha.

Jara is an inescapable part of life. Jara, the old age is of two types - Kāla Jara (Timely old age) and Akāla Jara (Early / Premature Ageing). The former type of Jara, i.e., Kāla jara, is

- 1 PG Scholar, Department of Maulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda), Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India
- 2 Assistant Professor, Department of Maulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda), Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India
- 3 Associate Professor, Department of Maulika Siddhanta (Basic Principles of Ayurveda), Amrita School of Ayurveda, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Amritapuri, India

Swabhāva or Sahaja in nature, which is cherished by everyone. Akārajara is an unnatural and untimely process, occurring ahead of time. This type of Jara induces a set of social problems, and mental agony, terminating in social stigma.

Different Opinions Regarding Ageing

- Swabhava - This means the process of deterioration occurs naturally. Svabhava literally means “inherent property,” “innate property,” “by nature itself,” or “natural constitution.” Svabhava is the name given to nature’s unique, invisible process. Acharya Charaka explained Svabhavoparamavada theory, which states that “there is a causative factor for the manifestation of beings but no such factor exists for their deterioration.” That is, the deterioration process occurs naturally.
- The growth and development of body parts is a natural phenomenon that occurs from conception to death. Furthermore, Susruta Samhita adds that Jara (old age) is a Swabhavika vyādhi.
- Lifespan of persons depends on 2 factors, Daiva (Deeds of previous life) and Purusha kara (Deeds of present life).
- कालस्य परिणामेन जरामृत्युनिमित्तजाः|
- रोगाः स्वाभाविका दृष्टाः स्वभावो निष्प्रतिक्रियः|| (Cha.Sha.1/115)
- That which takes place under the influence of Kala.
- कात्स्न्येन शरीरवृद्धिकरास्त्वमे [१] भावा भवन्ति; तद्यथा- कालयोगः, स्वभावसंसिद्धिः, आहारसौष्ठवम्, अविघातश्चेति|| (Cha.Sha.6/12)
- Shareera Vriddhikarabhava-abhava

Need of The Hour- Current Relevance

As a clinical specialty, geriatric medicine emerged in order to unravel the syndromes during the elderly such as progressive decline in fertility along with longevity. The roots of this branch have spread over the World particularly in the UK, Western European countries, North America, Australia, and New Zealand. By 2025, the number of elderly people is expected to rise more than 1.2 billion. There is a slow and steady growth of elderly population during the last few decades. The Chronological ageing process is an inevitable one and is not uniform across globally due to the difference in genetics, lifestyle and overall health practices followed. Ayurveda aimed at the Anayasa Jeevitham and Marana (Kala Mrithyu) especially in the elderly persons with

the Rasayana and the Vajeekarana. Most of the geriatric syndromes such as Arthritis, Asthma, Cancer, Cardiovascular diseases, Diabetes, Dementia, Mental health and Obesity etc. can be managed by following the guidelines of Ayurveda

Role of Ayurveda In Geriatric Nutrition

Ahara is mentioned as one among the three Upasthambas. According to Acharya Kashyapa, it is considered as Maha Bhaishajya. Ayurveda puts a huge emphasis on diet and dietary habits known as “Pathya”. Nutritional well-being and the enjoyment of food play an important role in the quality of life in older adults. Medicine without diet may be fruitless. So, a diet after sixty years should be nutritionally adequate and well balanced.

Aasapthathe (Above 70 years), is the Kala of Kshaya of Dhaathu, Indriya Sakthi and Ojas (Bala) (AH Saa. 3/105). The enchanted efficacy of Ahara is explained in the Mathraasitheeya Adhyaya of Ashtanga Hrudaya, Annapaana Vidhi Adhyaya of Charaka Samhita etc. All comprises the idea based to prevent the Kshaya which is the cause of Geriatric Syndromes. Since the sutra “Annam Brahma” narrates the importance of diet and lifestyle, the appropriate utilisation of this background can be utilised to overwhelm these syndromes to a large extent.

Nutritional wellbeing has a key role in determining the quality of life of a person especially during the elderly age. A set of Nithya Sevaneeya Aharas as well as Varjya Aharas mentioned in the Matrasitheeya Adhyaya of Ashtanga Hridaya Sūtrasthāna will help a person to follow a nutritional security by providing the nutritional requirements at these stages as well as to prevent the complications and chronicity of geriatric syndromes.

आहारसम्भवं वस्तु रोगाश्चाहारसम्भवाः।

हिताहितविशेषाच्च विशेषः सुखदुःखयोः॥ (Cha.Su.28/45)

Acharya Charaka calls ‘Vasthu’ (Physique and Mind) and Roga as Aahaara Sambhava, and that Hithahitha Sevana can make a person be in the state of ‘Vyaadhikumktha’ and attain eternal happiness.

The Pareekshakas (examiners) selected these types of diet since they are devoid of Rajas and Tamas and to increase the Sathvaguna of the person.

Probable Causes of Premature Ageing

The harmful Shareera Doshas are caused by the following Nidanas. They are Gramya Aahara, Kshara, Shushka Mamsa, Tila, Palala, Pishtanna, Viroodha Nava Shooka etc., Dhanya, Vishamashana, Adhyashana, Madyapana etc. The Viharaja Nidana told are Divasvapna, Ativyayama, Atisamkshobha, Ativyavaya etc. Manasika factors like Bhaya, Shoka, Krodha, Lobha, and Moha also play a major role. By all these Nidanas, Shareera Doshas are vitiated which are responsible for the unwanted changes in the body.

Role of Nityasevaneeya Ahara in Old Age

Raktha Sali, Shastika Sali, Godhuma, Yava, Jangala Mamsa, Sunishannaka, Jeevanthi, Baala Moolaka, Vasthuka, Triphala, Mrudhweeka, Patola, Mudga, Sarkara, Go Ghritha, Divyodaka, Ksheera, Kshodra, Dadima and Saidhava Lavana are the main diet indicated for the daily use which can be considered as balanced one since it satisfies the nutritional requirements and provide Carbohydrates, Proteins and Vitamins etc.

The Cereals and Pulses

Properties of Shashtika

स्निग्धो ग्राही लघुः स्वादुदुस्निदोषघ्नः स्थिरो हिमः॥
षष्टिको व्रीहिषु श्रेष्ठो गौरश्चासितगौरतः | (AH.Su.5/8)

Shashtika is a kind of rice which grows very quickly to maturity- within sixty days (meaning of Shashtika) which is Agrya among all Vreehi and is therefore light on digestion. It is rich in Carbohydrates, Potassium. Raktha Shali is a variety of rice, Sreshta among Sooka Dhaanya which is Trishnagna and Tridoshahara

Properties of Godhuma

वृष्यः शीतो गुरुः स्निग्धो जीवनो वातपित्तहा॥
सन्धानकारी मधुरो गोधूमः स्थैर्यकृत्सरः | (AH.Su.6/16)

Godhuma is Vrushya, Snigdha, Jeevana ,Vata Pitha Hara and Sandhana Kara. The Sthira Guna will enable the elderly to get a healthy and stable body stature. Carbohydrates are the main nutritional component of wheat. Still, this grain harbours significant amounts of fibre, which may aid your digestion.

Properties of Yava

रूक्षः शीतो गुरुः स्वादुः सरो विड्वातकृद्यवः॥१३॥

वृष्यः स्थैर्यकरो मूलमेदःपित्तकफान् जयेत्॥

पीनसश्वासकासोरुस्तम्भकण्ठत्वगामयान्॥(AH.Su.6/13-14)

Yava (Barley)'s Potassium, Folate, Iron, and Vitamin B-6 content, together with its lack of cholesterol, all support cardiovascular functions, one of the main syndromes in the elderly. Except the Vatakara property of Yava, all other properties like Vrushya, Sthairyakarattvam makes it ideal. It is used in Peenasa, Swasa, Kaasa, Kanda Rogas for Pulmonary as well as cardiovascular problem and to maintain a good lipid profile.

Properties of Mudga

मौद्गस्तु पथ्यः संशुद्धव्रणकण्ठाक्षिरोगिणाम्॥ (AH.Su.6/33)

Mudga is 'Agrya' or 'Vara' among Sookadhaanya since it causes less Vata. There are several health benefits for mung beans, such as, it helps in weight control, lowers blood pressure, lowers cholesterol and heart disease risk, may help fight cancer, boosts immunity, protects against infections, improves skin health, provides detoxification benefits, decreases PMS syndrome etc. Most of these benefits can be used by the elderly by making it into a variety of Kritha Annas like Soup (Rasa), Shashkuli, Upaseka and Upadamsa etc.

Vegetables and Fruits

Health Benefits of Draksha

द्राक्षा फलोत्तमा वृष्या चक्षुष्या सृष्टमूलविट्॥

स्वादुपाकरसा स्निग्धा सकषाया हिमा गुरुः॥

निहन्त्यनिलपित्तास्रतिक्तास्यत्वमदात्ययान्॥

तृष्णाकासश्रमश्वासस्वरभेदक्षतक्षयान्॥ (AH.Su.6/114)

Draksha (grapes) known as the Phalothama due to the properties such as Vrushya, Chakshushya (Gives Indriya Bala, especially for eye), easy excretion of Urine as well as Mala, Seetha Veerya and Snigdha. This is very useful in Vatapaithika Vyadhis, Trishna, Swaasa, Kshatha, Swara Kshaya associated with elderly people.

It is suitable for people with diabetes, as long as they are accounted for in the diet plan as raw or medicine forms such as Drakshadi Kashaya or Drakshadi Paana, Drakshadi Lehyam etc.

Health Benefits of Daadima

उद्रिक्तपित्ताञ्जयति लीन्दोषान्स्वादु दाडिमम्॥

पित्ताविरोधि नात्युष्णमम्लं वातकफापहम्॥

सर्वं हृद्यं लघु स्निग्धं ग्राहि रोचनदीपनम्॥ (AH.Su.6/118)

Daadima (Pomegranate) seeds get their vibrant red hue from Polyphenols. These chemicals are powerful antioxidants. The antioxidants in pomegranate juice can help remove free radicals, protect cells from damage. The Anorexia can be treated with a single fruit and its Pithavirodhi though contains amla Rasa.

The other fruits are excluded from Nithya Sevana and may be consumed seasonally as per Ritu Charya and availability such as Mocha (Banana) , Kharjoora (Dates), Panasa (Jackfruit). Naalikera (coconut), Aamra (Mango). Most of them are Swaadupaaka, Snigdha and Kapha Sukra Kritha and are rich in fibres and Vitamins. Vilwa, Kapitha, Peelu etc. also can be used for Swasa, Kasa, Constipation etc. as per the Vidhi.

Health Benefits of Triphala

त्रिफलां मधुसर्पिर्भ्यां निशि नेत्रबलाय च।

स्वास्थ्यानुवृत्तिकृद्यच्च रोगोच्छेदकरं च यत्॥ (AH.Su.8/44)

Consuming Triphala with Madhu and Ghritha in the night enhances vision, prevents Cataract and other ophthalmic problems, even Glaucoma. It also acts as a rejuvenating agent (Rasayana), is cost effective and Patient friendly (Palatable). It is 'Sarva Rogaghamni' and prevents the disease related cognition such as Parkinson's, Dementia etc.

Easy and Cost effective Rasayanas

Benefits of Rasayana

दीर्घमायुः स्मृतिं मेधामारोग्यं तरुणं वयः।

प्रभावर्णस्वरौदार्यं देहेन्द्रियबलं परम्॥

वाक्सिद्धिं प्रणतिं [३] कान्तिं लभते ना रसायनात्।

लाभोपायो हि शस्तानां रसादीनां रसायनम्॥ (Cha.Chi.1/8)

After proper detoxification process, administration of Customised and personalised Rasayanas will ensure the Deerghayu, Smrithi, Medha Sakthi, Taruna Vaya etc. in elderly.

पीताऽश्वगन्धा पयसाऽर्धमासं घृतेन तैलेन सुखाम्बुना वा।

कृशस्य पुष्टिं वपुषो विधत्ते बालस्य सस्यस्य यथा सुवृष्टिः॥

(AH.Uttara.39/157)

Aswagandha with Gritha/ Taila/ Sukaambu for 15 days.

दिने दिने कृष्णतिलप्रकुञ्चं समश्रतां शीतजलानुपानम्।

पोषः शरीरस्य भवत्यनल्पो दृढीभवन्त्यामरणाच्च दन्ताः॥

(AH.Su.39/158)

Krishna Tila in Morning with Cold water as Anupana

- Bringaraja (*Eclipta alba*) Swarasa with Ksheera
- Mandookaparni (*Centella asiatica*)Swarasa, Yasthimadhu (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) Choorna with Milk, Guduchi Swarasa, Sankha Pushpi Kalka etc.
- Narasimha Rasayana, Agasthya Rasayana, Chyavana Prasha, Abhayarishtam, Vardhamana Pippali Rasayana etc.

Conclusion

नित्यं हिताहारविहारसेवी समीक्ष्यकारी विषयेष्वसक्तः।

दाता समः सत्यपरः क्षमावानाप्तोपसेवी च भवत्यरोगः॥

(AH.Su.4/36)

The person who indulges daily in healthy foods and activities, who discriminates the good and bad of everything and then acts wisely, who is not attached too much to the objects of the senses, who develops the habit of charity, of considering all as equal, of truthfulness, of pardoning and keeping company of good persons only, becomes free from all diseases. Consequences of ageing troubles most people. By following the Ayurveda principles of diet, it is possible to slow down the process of ageing, restore physical and mental strength and prevent the consequences of ageing up to certain extent.

References

- Dr. Ketan Rathwa, Dr. Rakesh Salve **Concept of Rasayana in Ayurvedic Literature.** (n.d.). Retrieved September 19, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333564909_Concept_of_rasayana_in_ayurvedic_literature
- Meera E., Vinayan Shyam, Shrikanth P.H. **A review on Ageing and Anti-ageing measures in Ayurveda,** 2014
- Thakor, K., Negalur, V. B., Mishra, Y., Bhat, N., & B., S. (2016). Critical analysis of Nitya Sevaniya Ahara Dravya's - Balanced diet in Ayurveda. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Sciences (JAIMS)*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.21760/JAIMS.V1I1.3638>
- Caraka., Sharma P, Agniveśa., Drḍhabala. Carakasamhita. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 1983
- Vāgbhaṭa, Parādkaṛ H, Aruṇadatta, Hemādri. Aṣṭāṅgaḥṛdayam. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2000.

KIRANĀVALĪ
Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation
The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XIV.
Book III-IV
JULY – DECEMBER 2022

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram-36
Sanskritresearchfoundation@gmail.com